

Mass-Energy Equivalence: Fiery and Light Energy

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Abstract: The paper focuses only on the mass-energy equivalence, but not on Einstein's relativity theory. The kinetic energy defined in the classical mechanics play a vital role in the energy-mass equation and its applications. In this article, the author discusses about two bodies regarding the mass-energy relation: one is a rigid body and a body like the Sun which releases sunlight.

Keywords: classical mechanics, kinetic energy, sunlight, rocket mass

Mass-Energy Equivalence

The author reveals his own idea relating to the mass-energy equivalence, but his ideas do not relate to the mass-energy equivalence [1] defined in the Einstein's relativity theory. The author considers two moving bodies related to the mass-energy relation. One is a rigid body and a body like rocket mass.

The kinetic energy of a rigid body in motion is equal to $\frac{1}{2}$ (mass \times velocity).

Let us consider a moving rocket fully filled with fuel and moving in vacuum. The mass-energy equation of the rocket is:

$$E = mc^2 = mvc = pc,$$

where E is the fiery (fire) energy and light energy released from the moving rocket, m is the mass of the rocket, p is the momentum of the rocket, v is the velocity of the moving rocket, c is the speed of light.

When the fuel energy is decreasing from the moving rocket in vacuum (mass also decreases), the light energy is being released from the moving rocket until the rocket mass become zero. Let us observe the mass, momentum, energy, and velocity of the phenomenon.

If $m = 0$, then $p = 0$, $E = 0$, and v reaches to c .

This statement states the velocity of the rocket reaches to the speed of light when rocket mass becomes null.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C and Siqueira, A. M. O (2023) Mass-Energy Equivalence derived from Newtonian mechanics. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 9(8), 15963-01e. <https://www.doi.org/10.18540/jcecv19iss8pp15963-01e>